

Data quantity requirements for bone material property identification

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Abstract: Bone screws are used for fixing implants and stabilizing fractures. Correct torquing of these screws is important for positive patient outcomes. While some models have been presented to identify bone strength, no work has been done investigating how much data is required for these models to accurately make predictions. This work investigates the effect of varying data lengths on the identified strength values and confidence intervals. As the data length increased, the identified value converged and stabilized. In our case, about 6-8 turns of the screw were required for convergence. The 95% confidence intervals also narrowed, although more than expected.

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I. Introduction

Bone screws are commonly used in orthopedic surgery to fix implants in place or stabilize fractured bones. Over- or under-torquing these screws can lead to thread stripping or insufficient fixation, respectively; both effects may cause implant failure and/or tissue damage, potentially leading to additional complications or necessitate revision surgery. Hence, correct torquing of bone screws is important for positive patient outcomes.[1]

Bone screws are often tightened in an ad-hoc manner. This is typically successful, but misjudgment may result in inappropriate torque application. Varying surgeon skill and bone density may lead to additional inconsistencies[1]. It has been proposed that a model-based method can be used to identify the material properties of bone during the screw insertion process[2], and that these properties can then be used to recommend or enforce optimal insertion torques. If successful, this could reduce fixation failures and increase the probability of positive patient outcomes.

Some previous models have been proposed to enable optimal insertion[2,3], and have been tested for identifiability[1,2]. However, the models have not yet been assessed with respect to the required amount of data per test to ensure representative results with minimal noise effects. This is also related to the problem of estimating the confidence of predictions, so that a system can avoid making erroneous suggestions when the amount of data is insufficient. Hence, these issues must be directly considered. Therefore, in this paper, we investigate how the identified material properties change in relation to the data quality and quantity per test.

II. Methods

Recorded datasets from screw insertions were transformed into varying-length subsets. Parameter identification was performed on every subset, and the identified values were

plotted with respect to the amount of data in the subset used for the identification.

II.I. Data Collection

An HB65 bone screw (defined in ISO 3835:1991 [4]) was driven into 3mm holes (new hole for each test) in bone-mimicking[5] rigid polyurethane(PU) foam(SikaBlock® M80, Sika Services AG). This was repeated 4 times. This was driven using a high-torque closed-loop stepper motor system (34HS46-6004D-E1000 with CL86T driver, OMC Corp. Ltd.), and the torque and angular displacement were measured at 100 Hz using an inline torque sensor (NCTE-2300-20-1-AU-0-0, NCTE AG).

II.II. Modelling

The screw insertion model is a simplified version of the model derived in [3], drawing heavily from [6]. The model, summarized in eqn. 1, calculates the screw insertion torque, T_z [Nm] from the material strength, σ_{uts} [Pa], the bone-screw friction coefficient, μ [N/N], the displacement, ϕ [rad], the angular length of the thread-cutting section of the screw, α [rad], and the geometric parameters, G_1 [m³] and G_2 [m³/rad].

$$T_z(\phi) = \sigma_{uts}G_1 + \mu\sigma_{uts}\left(\phi + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right)G_2 \quad (1)$$

II.III. Data Analysis

The data from the screw insertions was processed in MATLAB R2020a. The data was manually trimmed to the period of screw insertion, and the displacement offset from the encoder was manually corrected. The datasets from every screw insertion were processed independently.

For each dataset, a subset containing the first 10 data points was made, then a subset containing the first 20, and so on, increasing in steps of 10 points, until the last subset contained all the data points in the dataset. For each subset, parameter identification was performed using the model in

eqn. 1; this was done using simple linear least squares fitting (with MATLAB's "fitlm()"), with σ_{uts} being the only unknown. The standard error from fitlm was also used to determine the 95% ($\pm 2\sigma$) confidence interval for each parameter identification.

III. Results and discussion

The plots of identified strength with increasing data size (from increasing insertion distance into the material) are shown in Fig. 1. The initial estimates vary greatly, and are highly inaccurate, but start to converge at about 3 turns. Most of the lines stabilize after about 6-8 turns, however none of the experiments tested clearly reached a steady state. Additionally, the identified strength values fall well below the datasheet value of 0.9 MPa; however, this could be explained with several factors. The torque sensor is rated to measure from a minimum of 0.2Nm, while the readings here (Seen in Fig. 2) fall below this range, which brings the measurement accuracy into question. Additionally, the model assumes the normal and friction stress from the hole stays constant as the screw is inserted, but it is possible that the screw may abrade the hole as it is inserted, steadily reducing this stress, resulting in lower-than-expected torque/identified strength values. The manual correction of encoder displacement offset may also introduce some bias. Lastly, there may be significant manufacturing variation in the material. Some of these problems may be alleviated by testing with a harder material, which would increase the torque, making the torque fall within the recommended range of the sensor, and increasing the SNR.

Figure 1. Refinement of estimated bone strength as data length is increased. Shaded areas represent the 95% confidence intervals.

The confidence intervals also present interesting features. It is normally expected that the confidence interval would become more refined as more data is included, and that the real/final identified value should mostly fit within the confidence intervals of the smaller subsets. However, this is not the case here. This may be due to the simple linear model, which does not capture all the behavior of the system. For example, a potential sinusoidal modulation from inserting a misaligned screw would be assumed by the fitting algorithm to be part of the gaussian noise, but it may cause systematic errors, resulting in fluctuations outside the expected confidence intervals. An example can be seen in Fig. 2 by considering the data around 1.7-1.9 turns; the

torque slope appears to go upwards more than the rest of the graph, which, assuming a straight line with gaussian noise, would give reasonable confidence that the material strength (related to torque slope) is much stronger than it is. There are more peaks and troughs in Fig. 2, so the data is clearly not just a straight line with gaussian noise, suggesting that the model can be expanded, or the experimental methodology improved.

Figure 2. Data from one screw insertion, with the reconstructed linear fit line from the regression/identified strength.

IV. Conclusions

Under the tested circumstances, the identified strength stabilized after about 6-8 turns. This may vary with material and screw/hole geometry, so more thorough testing is recommended. The final values were not in close agreement with each other and the datasheet, this could be due to several potential experimental issues, which should be addressed in future work. The confidence intervals of the identified values were much smaller than expected, which could indicate experimental problems, or that either additional features should be included in the model, or that the model should only be identified in a subset of the data.

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